

MEDICAL SCIENCES

TRITERPENE GLYCOSIDES FROM THE TUBERS OF *CYCLAMEN ADZHARICUM* POBED. AND THEIR STANDARDIZATION

Tabatadze N.,

Associate Professor, Sokhumi State University
Tbilisi, Georgia

Tsomaia I.,

Professor, Georgian Technical University
Tbilisi, Georgia

Chikovani A.,

Associate Professor, Sokhumi State University
Tbilisi, Georgia

Churgulia E.

Assistant Professor, Sokhumi State University
Tbilisi, Georgia

Abstract

Phytochemical studies of the tubers of *Cyclamen adzharicum* have shown that the total amount of triterpene saponins is less than 17 glycosides. Nine individual compounds have been isolated and characterized from the tubers. Two new glycosides – **Cyclamen M** and **Cyclamen F**, also the new aglycone of Cyclamen F were isolated and described for the first time from this species of *Cyclamen* genus.

High performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the qualitative and quantitative determination of the triterpene saponins in the raw material and in the purified crude saponins of *Cyclamen adzharicum*. HPLC profiles and quantification of major saponin - **Cyclamen N** were realized. Total content of triterpene saponins is 11.75% (Cyclamen N – 3.98%) in the raw material and 90.6% (Cyclamen N – 33.9%) in the purified crude saponins. Besides, content of the major glycosides – Cyclamen K, Q, G is 12.88%, 22.57% and 7.3%, respectively, in the purified crude saponins of *Cyclamen*.

Antifungal, antiprotozoal and antioxidant activities of several glycosides and enriched fractions have been investigated. Monodesmosides – **Cyclamen K** and **G** were evaluated for their fungicidal and antiprotozoal effects against *C. tropicalis* (MIC 12.5 µ/ml), *Leishmania infantum* and *Trichomonas vaginalis* (IC₅₀ < 1µ/ml). The sum of saponins exhibited a strong antifungal effect on *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis* and *Cryptococcus neoformans* (MIC 0.015µ/ml). Monodesmosides **Cyclamen K** and **G**, also sum of saponins were distinguished by high anti-tumor activity against A 549 lung carcinoma and DLD-1 intestinal carcinoma cells (IC₅₀ 2.0 µ/ml, 2.0 µ/ml, 5.2 µ/ml and 8.0 µ/ml, respectively).

Triterpene glycoside - **Cyclamen Q** exhibited a strong antioxidant activity (ORAC, µmol/Trolox/mg 0.052±0.004).

Keywords: Triterpene saponins, Cyclamen, HPLC, antifungal, antiprotozoal, cytotoxic activity.

Cyclamen adzharicum Pobed. (fam. Primulaceae) is an endemic plant of Georgia [1]. Phytochemical investigations of this plant showed that the tubers of *Cyclamen* contains a large amount of triterpene saponins. In traditional medicine, the the tubers of *C. adzharicum* were used for the treatment of highmoritis, frontitis, ethmoditis [2,3].

In order to identify biologically active substances and to determine their pharmacological activities, we have developed an effective method of separation and purification the sum of saponins from the tubers of the plant, fractionation and division into individual compounds.

Studies have shown that the total amount of saponins is less than 17 glycosides. Nine individual compounds have been isolated, named Cyclamen D, F, G, K, L, M, N, P and Q. The chemical structures of 7 individual molecules were established on the basis of physical-chemical methods, by 1D and 2D NMR experiments (1H, 13C, gs-COSY, gs-HMBC, gs-HMQC, DEPT, NOESY and gs-HSQC-TOCSY) and mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF, ESI-HR-MS) [4-9].

Cyclamens are the derivatives of different aglycones, such as: cyclamiretin A, anagalligenin B, 13β,28-epoxy-16α,23-dihydroxyolean, 16α-hydroxy-olean-12-eno-30,28-lactone, 16α,28-dihydroxy-olean-12-en-30-oic acid, 16α-hydroxy-13,28-epoxy-30,30-dibutoxyolean.

Cyclamen D – 3β-0- β-D-Xylp(1→2)- β-D-Glcp(1→4)- α-L-Arap cyclamiretin A.

Cyclamen G - 3β-0- β-D-Xylp(1→2)-β-D-Glcp(1→4)- [β-D-Glcp(1→2)]-α-L-Arap cyclamiretin A.

Cyclamen K – 13β,28-epoxy-3β-0-[β-D-Xylp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→4)-α-L-Arap-oxi]-16α,23-dihydroxi-olean.

Cyclamen N - 3β-0-[β-D-Glcp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→6)]-[β-D-Xylp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→4)-α-L-Arap-oxi] -16α-hydroxy-olean-12-eno-30,28-lactone.

Cyclamen Q – 3β-0-[β-D-Glcp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→6)]-[β-D-Xylp(1→2)]-[β-D-Glcp(1→4)-α-L-Arap-oxi] -16α,28-dihydroxy-olean-12-en-30-oic acid.

Cyclamen M – 3 β -O-[[β -D-Glcp(1 \rightarrow 2)]-[[β -D-Xylp(1 \rightarrow 2)]-[[β -D-Glcp(1 \rightarrow 3)]-[[β -D-Glcp(1 \rightarrow 4)]- α -L-Arap-anagalligenin B.

Cyclamen F – 3 β -O-[[β -D-Xylp(1 \rightarrow 2)]-[[β -D-Glcp(1 \rightarrow 2)]-[[β -D-Glcp(1 \rightarrow 4)]- α -L-Arap-16 α -hydroxy-13,28-epoxy-30,30-dibutoxyolean.

Cyclamen M and Cyclamen F, also the aglycon of Cyclamen F are new compounds. These glycosides and aglycon are described for the first time in this plant.

High-performance liquid chromatography method has been developed for the qualitative and quantitative determination of the triterpene saponins in the raw material and in the purified crude saponins of *Cyclamen adzharicum*. The mixture of water (with addition of 0.1M phosphoric acid) - acetonitrile was used as a mobile phase with a gradient condition. All solutions were of HPLC purity, the concentrations of the saponins and standards were 1 mg/ml, for purified crude saponins 10 mg/ml in MeOH. Solid phase - μ Bondapak C-18 reversed phase column, 300X3.9mm (UV detector 486), flow rate 1 ml/min, injection of samples - 20 μ l, run time 55 min. UV detection was performed at 205 nm [10].

The samples of the pure triterpene saponins were isolated from the crude extract of the tubers of *C. adzharicum*. The samples solutions were stored at the room temperature before use. The raw material of *C. adzharicum* (collected in Kobuleti, Velistsikhe, Georgia, dried in the shade). the purified crude saponins of the tubers were obtained mainly by three steps: dry tubers (61g) were extracted with methanol (600 ml) at 20°C by using column chromatography. Obtained extract was concentrated under vacuum and liophilised. After liophilisation dry extract (18 g) was purified on column of Poliamid SC6 in the gradient (methanol-water 0:100 \rightarrow 100:0) regime of elution. All solutions for HPLC analysis were filtered through a Millipore (0.45 μ m) filter.

The satisfactory results of separation of purified crude saponins were obtained in the gradient regime of elution: during 0-35 min water-acetonitrile \rightarrow 75:25, after 35-38 min water-acetonitrile \rightarrow 65:35 and 39-55 min water-acetonitrile \rightarrow 75:25.

As a HPLC chromatogram showed, there are about 14 triterpene saponins in the purified crude saponins and 7 of them are major compounds. On the basis of the retention time, using corresponding samples of triterpene glycosides, there have been identified 4 monodesmoside saponins of *C. adzharicum*: Cyclamen G (r.t. 33.197), Cyclamen N (r.t. 19.190), Cyclamen Q (r.t. 9.439) and Cyclamen K (r.t. 3.250). All the above mentioned glycosides elute between 3 and 34 min. The glycosides similar structures were isolated for the first time in this species of *Cyclamen* genus.

For quantification purposes the major glycoside of the tubers – Cyclamen N was used as an external standard, it was determined linearity of the purified crude saponins of *C. adzharicum*. The areas under the peaks and the corresponding concentration were used to plot the calibration graphs. The calibration graphs were linear. The regressions for Cyclamen N (conc. range 0.063125-1.01mg/ml) was $R^2=0.9994$, for the purified crude saponins (conc. range 0.658125-10.53mg/ml) $R^2=0.9994$.

The reproducibility of the method was evaluated by analyzing three tests of controls at 3 separate days and calculating the relative standard deviation 2.1248%.

Thus, High performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the qualitative and quantitative determination of the triterpene saponins of the tubers of *Cyclamen adzharicum*. Using HPLC method 14 triterpene saponins were determined, 4 of them (Cyclamen N, G, K, Q) were identified by using corresponding samples. Total content of triterpene saponins is 11.75% (Cyclamen N – 3.98%) in the raw material and 90.6% (Cyclamen N – 33.9%) in the purified crude saponins. Besides, the content of the major glycosides – Cyclamen K, Q, G is 12.88%, 22.57% and 7.3%, respectively, in the purified crude saponins of *Cyclamen*.

This HPLC method, applied to qualitative and quantitative analysis of triterpenes from the tubers of *Cyclamen adzharicum*, proves to be efficient and reproducible.

Biological studies have shown the antifungal, antiprotozoal, antioxidant and cytotoxic effects of *Cyclamen* tubers's saponins extract and individual glycosides [2].

The fungicidal and antiprotozoal activities of individual substances and enriched fractions from the tubers of *Cyclamen* were studied in the Laboratory of Botany and Parasitology of the faculty of Pharmacy at the University of Mediterranean (Marseille, France).

The antifungal activity has been determined against yeasts and dermatophytes with an agar dilution method as previously described [11]. The tested concentration range was 1-2 mg/ml for saponins extract, and 0.06 μ g/ml to 200 μ g/ml for the individual compounds. The reference antifungal agents were amphotericin B for yeasts and ketokonazole for dermatophytes. The minimal inhibitory concentration of saponins has been determined.

The highest antifungal activity was obtained with tuber's saponins extract against *C. glabrata*, *C. parapsilosis* and *C. Cryptococcus neoformans* (MIC 0.015 μ g/ml). Monodesmosides – Cyclamen K and G were effective against *C. tropicalis* (MIC 12.5 μ g/ml).

The antiprotozoal activities against *Leishmania infantum* and *Trichomonas vaginalis* have been evaluated as described in [12]. The inhibitory concentration (IC50) and lethal dose (LD100) were determined with amphotericin B and metronidazole as references, respectively.

The most active products against *Trichomonas vaginalis* were monodesmosides – **Cyclamens K** and **G** (IC50 <1 μ g/ml). The sum of saponins of *Cyclamen* was also characterized by interesting antiprotozoal activity (IC50 1.75 μ g/ml).

Glycoside - **Cyclamen Q** exhibited the highest antioxidant (ORAC test, Trolox/mg) activity (0.052 \pm 0.004).

The cytotoxic activities of sum of saponins and individual glycosides from the tubers of *Cyclamen adzharicum* have been studied against skin fibrosarcoma L929, intestinal adenocarcinoma DLD-1, lung

carcinoma A 549 and prostate adenocarcinoma PC 3 tumor cells at the laboratories of the Universities of Clermont-Ferrand (France) and Quebec (Canada).

The sum of saponins showed high cytotoxic efficiency, at a concentration of 100 µg/ml 100% destruction of tumor cells was observed.

Cyclamen K and **Cyclamen G** were evaluated for their cytotoxicity against lung and intestinal carcinoma cells. The most active product against A 549 and DLD-1 was Cyclamen K (IC₅₀ 2.0 µg/ml in both cases) compared to Cyclamen G (IC₅₀ 5.2 µg/ml and 8.0 µg/ml respectively).

It should be noted that sum of saponins (IC₅₀ 8.2 µg/ml) and Cyclamen K (IC₅₀ 1.26 µg/ml) and Cyclamen G (IC₅₀ 4.4 µg/ml) damage normal cells as well, so it is characterized by non-specific cytotoxic action.

It is known that *Cyclamen* juice and extract have been used in traditional folk medicine for the treatment of headaches. The headache was probably caused by inflammatory processes in the nasal appendages and pain relief was due to the content of biologically active substances - triterpene saponins in the *Cyclamen* extract [1].

At the Department of Biological Research, Iovel Kutateladze Institute of Pharmacochemistry, the anti-inflammatory, mucus-thinning and anti-sinusitis efficacy of sum saponins of *Cyclamen* have been evaluated. It was established to provoke a strong reflex reaction in the nasal mucosa and nasal appendages. The therapeutic action of *Cyclamen* saponins is due to the stimulation of the secretory activity of the covering epithelium in the nasal cavity and appendages. A reflex reaction also occurs in the sinus mucosa. Reflexively enhances the secretory activity of the seromucosal glands, thus providing enhanced drainage of the paranasal sinuses [3].

For the Institute of Pharmacochemistry Georgian National Intellectual Property Center „Sakpatenti“ has made a positive decision on the useful model of *Cyclamen* „The obtaining method of triterpene saponins with anti-inflammatory action of the nose and appendages“. Through experimental research the complete chemical composition of the tubers of *Cyclamen* was studied and the normative-technical documentation required for the creation and registration of a prescription drug for the treatment of sinusitis was developed [13].

Thus, Using botanical, phytochemical and pharmacological research, it can be concluded that *Cyclamen adzharicum* growing in Georgia, due to their raw material base, high content of triterpene saponins and anti-inflammatory efficacy, can be used for the release of an effective and harmless drug form, that's expanding the arsenal of herbal remedies for the treatment of sinusitis.

References

1. Flora of Georgia, X, edit. 2, Tbilisi, „Mecniereba“, 1985, 90-96.
2. Tabidze B. Avtoreferat PhD, Tbilisi, 2006, 46 p.
3. Gedevanishvili M.D., Tsereteli I.P., Andguladze I.G. Chemistry and biology of the active compounds from the medicinal plants of Georgia, „Mecniereba“ Tbilisi, 1969, 202-206.
4. Tabidze B., Tabatadze N., Zviadadze L., Sutiashvili M., Elias R., Faure R., Balansard G., Kemertelidze E. Georgia Chemical Journal, 2005, 5(4), 381-385.
5. Tabidze B. V., Tabatadze N., Dekanosidze G. E., Elias R., Faure R. Chemistry of Natural Compounds, 2009, 5, 556-558.
6. Tabidze B., Tabatadze N., Mshvildadze V., Elias R., Canlet C., Balansard G., Kemertelidze E. Bulletin of the Georgian Academy of Sciences, 2005, 171, 1, 73-77.
7. Tabidze B., Tabatadze N., Mshvildadze V., Sutiashvili M., Elias R., Canlet C., Dekanosidze G., Balansard G. Georgia Chemical Journal, 2004, 4(2), 157-160.
8. Tabidze B. Ethnopharmacologia, dossier special „Medicine traditionnelle de Georgie“, 2011, 47.
9. Tabidze B., Tabatadze N., Mshvildadze V., Getia M., Dekanosidze G. Collection of Scientific Works XLVIII, TSMU, 2014, 141-143.
10. Tabidze B., Tabatadze N., Elias R., Dekanosidze G., Balansard G., Kemertelidze E. Georgia Chemical Journal, 2004, 4(2), 161-164.
11. Favel A., Steinmetz M.D., Regli P. et al. Planta Medica, 1994, 60, 1, 50-53.
12. Delmas F., Gasquet M., Timon-David P. et al. J. Europ. J. Med. Chem., 1993, 28, 1, 23.
13. Dekanosidze G., Tabidze B., Mshvildadze V., Getia M. Georgian National Intellectual Property Center „Sakpatenti“, utility model, 2014, №555/02.